

SYMPATHY AND EMPATHY AS PSYCHOLINGUISTIC PHENOMENA: A PSYCHOLOGICAL AND LINGUISTIC PERSPECTIVE

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This study aims to examine sympathy and empathy from a psychological and psycholinguistic perspective, focusing on their internal cognitive nature and external verbal realisation. Drawing on the theoretical views of scholars such as D. Goleman, L. Vygotsky, and A. A. Leontiev, the research considers sympathy and empathy as internal psychological processes that are transformed into speech through inner speech mechanisms. The paper also highlights the semantic and pragmatic differences in the verbal expression of sympathy and empathy in English and Uzbek, demonstrating that similar expressions do not always produce identical emotional effects. The findings suggest that sympathy and empathy should be regarded not only as emotional reactions but also as complex psycholinguistic phenomena realised through communicative speech acts.

Sympathy and empathy are complex emotional phenomena that occupy an important place in both psychology and linguistics. Despite their frequent use in everyday communication, these concepts lack a unified theoretical interpretation, which complicates their linguistic analysis.

Sympathy and empathy are also feelings. However, world scientists have the same attitude to the concept of feelings and emotions. If we touch on psycholinguistic theoretical ideas about sympathy and empathy, we consider it appropriate to cite the following opinion of N.Mikhailchuk, L.Onufrieva about the study of feelings from a linguistic perspective: "*However, the lack of a comprehensive theory of emotions, the diversity and contradiction of their classifications, the heterogeneity of the processes of their definition complicate the study of verbalization of human emotional reactions*". According to this opinion, N.Mikhailchuk, L.Onufrieva believe that due to the lack of a single and perfect theory in the study of emotions, they are interpreted differently. If we analyze this view in relation to the object of our research, sympathy and empathy are also interpreted differently from the perspective of psychology and linguistics. For example, in psychology, sympathy is defined as goodwill towards others, empathy is defined as feeling the inner state of another person. However, in linguistics, these two phenomena often have similar meanings when expressed in speech. In Uzbek, expressions such as "*hamdardman*", "*rahmim keldi*", "*achindim*" are associated with sympathy and empathy, while in English, these phenomena are expressed with expressions such as "*I'm sorry for you*", "*I feel for you*", "*I can imagine how you feel*". However, their semantics and emotional impact do not always match. Therefore, it is precisely these uncertainties that are problematic and require a solution when comparing the expression of emotions through language.

According to D.Goleman, empathy is an emotional ability. In addition, the scientist considers empathy to be, first of all, a phenomenon related to perception and understanding, and then a process related to feeling another person through language in speech, expressing his

state through language combinations. Empathy and sympathy are internal psychological processes. In connecting internal psychic processes with speech, it is appropriate to turn to the issue of language and thinking. The psycholinguistic scientist L.Vygotsky expresses the following idea about thinking and speech: "*Inner speech... is not speech minus sound but a speech function that is unique in its structure and function.*" According to this idea, the scientist said that inner speech is an internal form of external speech and is important in the development of thinking. These ideas of L.Vygotsky show that phenomena such as sympathy and empathy are internal psychic processes and that inner speech is a stage that prepares human thinking and feelings for external speech. Sympathy and empathy, which are the objects of our research, also arise primarily as internal psychological processes and perceive the pain, joy or anxiety of the interlocutor in inner speech. At the next stage, a linguistic process occurs, and feelings are transferred to a linguistic form: "*I understand you*", "*I share your pain*". From this idea, we can conclude: sympathy and empathy are not just emotional processes, but complex psycholinguistic phenomena that arise in the unity of thinking and language.

A.A.Leontiev calls feelings speech acts used to satisfy a communicative need. This approach of the scientist is very appropriate in considering sympathy and empathy as speech acts. Because these two phenomena arise from the purpose of communication with the interlocutor.

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